

Research

Investigating Privacy Security Risks for Elderly Individuals in Telemedicine: A Survey-Based Analysis

Ji Jiangming^{1*}, Akwanwi Lourine Azanwi¹

¹Department of Computer Technology, College of Information Engineering, Huzhou University, No.1 Xueshi Road, 313000, Huzhou, Zhejiang, China

Abstract: Since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, healthcare systems have undergone significant transformations to enhance accessibility, improve health outcomes, and reduce costs. Among these changes, telemedicine has emerged as a popular avenue for delivering medical services, allowing patients to receive care remotely. However, the adoption of telemedicine among older individuals, who often require specialized medical attention due to age-related health issues, has been slow. This reluctance to embrace telemedicine exacerbates healthcare disparities, particularly among the elderly population.

This project aims to investigate privacy and security threats faced by elderly individuals in the context of telemedicine. Specifically, the study seeks to analyze data collected from a survey of 500 individuals aged 60 and above to identify prevalent privacy concerns among the elderly in Cameroon.

A survey-based approach will be employed to gather insights into the privacy and security concerns of older individuals regarding telemedicine. The survey will be designed to capture demographic information, assess perceptions of privacy risks associated with telemedicine. Logistic regression analysis will be conducted to explore associations between demographic factors and privacy concerns.

The study findings will provide an understanding of the privacy and security challenges faced by elderly individuals in telemedicine. Logistic regression analysis will reveal demographic factors influencing privacy concerns among older adults. This research contributes to improving privacy and security measures in telemedicine for elderly individuals by identifying existing privacy and security concerns and bringing to light where to better improve it. By addressing these challenges, healthcare providers and policymakers can promote the equitable access and utilization of telemedical services among the elderly, thereby enhancing overall healthcare delivery and outcomes.

Keywords: Elderly people; privacy security; telemedicine; privacy risk; security risk; and protection mechanism.

*Corresponding Author

Accepted: 29 May, 2024; **Published:** 30 May, 2024

How to cite this article: Ji Jiangming, Akwanwi Lourine Azanwi (2024). *Investigating Privacy Security Risks for Elderly Individuals in Telemedicine: A Survey-Based Analysis*. *North American Academic Research*, 7(5), 214-224. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12734979>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2023 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

Telemedicine, involves the use of technology to provide medical care to patients who are not physically present at a healthcare facility. It has gained significance, especially in recent epidemic situations, for delivering remote clinical services, improving disease control, managing clinical cases, and conducting epidemiological research (Zhou X, 2020).

The integration of mobile healthcare and virtual care into the healthcare system aims to enhance healthcare delivery, offering services such as medical care, consultations, diagnosis, data transmission, guidance, and treatment via real-time interactive communication (MA, 2020). It covers various communication methods, including Internet Protocol (IP) voice calls, video consultations, and telephone calls (Okerefor K, 2020). These devices are now also given to patients who are in hospitals or quarantines, reducing the chance of exposure to other persons. (O., 2020) (Greenhalgh T, 2020). Asynchronous consultations, on the other hand, are useful for non-urgent cases and follow-ups, where patients can submit requests, images, and descriptions for later evaluation (Leite H., 2020).

Mobile healthcare services are particularly beneficial for older individuals who are the primary users (Vidal-Alaball J, 2020). This healthcare approach can be synchronous or asynchronous. Synchronous platforms enable real-time sessions between patients and doctors, facilitating the exchange of critical data (Grimes CL, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic, caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, has primarily affected the elderly and individuals with underlying medical conditions (Hui DS, 2020). Mobile healthcare services, including telemedicine, have emerged as effective tools to address this crisis by ensuring healthcare access while minimizing the risk of exposure. Many countries have adapted their regulations to enable the use of mobile healthcare in hospitals and health facilities, facilitating patient access to medical care (Cho H, 2020) (M., 2020). Virtual care solutions, such as telemedicine, can reduce the virus's spread and protect healthcare professionals by minimizing in-person visits and face-to-face interactions (Zhai Y, 2020). Telemedicine also offers post-hospitalization follow-up, even for elderly patients in facilities, with remote assessments (AJ., 2020) (AJ., Exploring the adoption of telemedicine and virtual software for the care of outpatients during and after the COVID-19 pandemic., 2021) (AJ., Application of telemedicine and e-health technology for clinical services in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, 2021). These services have proven valuable in hospital settings, including assisting nurses in caring for COVID-19 patients and providing rehabilitation programs in intensive care units (AJ., Application of telemedicine and e-health technology for clinical services in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, 2021). While telemedicine holds promise, it presents challenges for older patients, including disparities in access to necessary resources such as the internet, potentially aggravating existing healthcare inequalities (Baciu A, 2017 Jan 11). The digital healthcare divide is a concern, as not everyone has equal access to technology and the skills required to use it effectively (Mackert M, 2016 Oct 04.) (Vulpe S, 2020 Mar.). This divide is particularly relevant to the elderly, contributing to disparities in digital outcomes (Riggins FJ, 2005) (communities, 2010.) (Wei KK, 2011). The rising popularity of telemedicine among the elderly highlights the need to address potential privacy and security risks. Elderly individuals are more susceptible to cybersecurity threats and may lack knowledge about privacy and security issues. Thus, investigating these risks and developing protection mechanisms is essential.

Methodology

Model Construction Process

- ✓ Collected survey data from 500 individuals aged 60 and above, capturing demographic information, telemedicine app usage, concerns, and protection mechanisms, and pre-processing the survey data.
- ✓ Encode categorical variables, transforming them into numerical values for the model such as levels of concern.
- ✓ Analyze the distribution and relationships of variables through descriptive statistics and data visualization.
- ✓ Identify potential correlations and trends between demographic factors, usage patterns, and privacy concerns.
- ✓ Divide the data set into a training set and a test set. For instance, use 70% of the data for training the model and 30% for testing its performance.
- ✓ Utilize logistic regression to build the model on the training data.
- ✓ Logistic regression estimates coefficients for each variable, indicating how they influence the likelihood of expressing privacy concerns.

- ✓ Evaluate the model's performance on the test set using various metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and the confusion matrix.
- ✓ Assess how well the model predicts privacy concerns based on the provided demographic and usage data.

Search method

The study used a survey approach to collect data from senior people aged 60 and above who had been exposed to telemedicine. The design allowed for a one-time data collection, including participants' existing perspectives and experiences with privacy and security threats, as well as what they would like to see changed. A representative sample of 500 old people from diverse locations or healthcare settings in Cameroon was chosen using a categorized random sampling technique. To ensure diversity in the sample, classification is based on age groups and levels of exposure to technology.

Data Collection

A comprehensive survey questionnaire with items such as age, gender, education, marital status, and prior experience with telemedicine was established. Some privacy concerns questions include assessing participants' privacy concerns regarding the usage of mobile healthcare services and how frequently they use telemedical apps, as well as assessing participants' awareness of Privacy Measures:

What kinds of mobile healthcare apps are they used to, and how worried are they with your personal information's privacy and security when using these telemedical apps? Inquire about their specific privacy and security concerns when using telemedical apps, as well as their knowledge of any protection mechanisms available for these telemedical apps, the types of protection mechanisms they believe would be useful for telemedical apps, and how satisfied they are with these protection mechanisms. Their concerns about the privacy and security of the telemedical apps they utilize. Evaluating whether they have ever stopped using a telemedical app owing to privacy or security concerns, and how important privacy and security are to them.

Based on participant choices and accessibility, the survey was delivered via in-person interviews and online platforms. The variables in the data are as follows:

The dependent variable is the level of concern about privacy and security, which was measured using categories such as "Very concerned," "Moderately concerned," "Slightly concerned," and "Not concerned." We can convert these categories into a binary outcome by considering "Very concerned" as 1 (indicating high concern) and all other categories as 0 (indicating low concern).

The independent variables (age, gender, education level, marital status, mobile healthcare usage, specific concerns, awareness of protection mechanisms, user experience, and importance level) to assess how they influence the likelihood of being "Very concerned" about privacy and security in telemedicine.

TABLE 1. Demographic Characteristics of The Respondents

<i>Interview Record</i>	<i>variable type</i>	<i>value</i>	<i>details</i>
<i>Gender</i>	categorical variable	male	male =194
		female	female =306
		other	other = 0
<i>Age</i>	continuous variable	60-65	60-65 = 250
		66-70	66-70 =139
		70-....	70-.... =111
<i>Education</i>	categorical variable	High school or below	High school or below =250
		Bachelor's degree	Bachelor's degree =139
		Master's degree	Master's degree = 100
		Doctoral Degree	Doctoral degree =11

<i>Marital status</i>	categorical variable	Single/other	Single/other = 29
		Married	Married = 255
		Divorced	Divorced = 100
		Widowed	Widowed = 116
<i>Frequency of Usage</i>	categorical variable	Daily	Daily = 129
		Several times a week,	Several times a week =55
		Once a week	Once a week = 55
		Rarely	Rarely = 250
<i>Types of Apps Used</i>	categorical variable	Fitness tracking	Fitness tracking =300
		Medication reminders	Medication reminders = 100
		Telemedicine/Video consultations.	Telemedicine/Video consultations = 10
		Health information resources	Health information resources = 250
		Symptom trackers	Symptom trackers = 200
<i>Privacy Concerns</i>	categorical variable	Very concerned	Very concerned = 333
		Moderately concerned	Moderately concerned = 66
		Slightly concerned	Slightly concerned = 50
		Not concerned	Not concerned = 51
<i>Specific Concerns</i>	categorical variable	Unauthorized access	Unauthorized access = 300
		Data breaches	Data breaches = 250
		Inadequate encryption	Inadequate encryption = 50
		Insecure storage of data	Insecure storage of data = 200
		Sharing of data with third parties without consent	Sharing of data with third parties without consent = 400
<i>Awareness of Protection</i>	categorical variable	yes	yes = 150
		no	no = 350
<i>Importance Level</i>	categorical variable	Very important	Very important = 400
		Moderately important	Moderately important = 40
		Slightly important	Slightly important = 35
		Not important	Not important = 25
<i>Satisfaction level</i>	categorical variable	Very satisfied	Very satisfied = 60
		Moderately satisfied	Moderately satisfied = 200
		Slightly satisfied	Slightly satisfied = 110
		Not satisfied	Not satisfied = 130

Data Analysis

We used logistic regression to analyze the survey data, which is suitable for analyzing binary outcomes or categorical dependent variables. In this paper, the dependent variable is the level of concern about privacy and security, which was measured using categories such as "Very concerned," "Moderately concerned," "Slightly concerned," and "Not concerned." We converted these categories into a binary outcome by considering "Very concerned" as 1 (indicating high concern) and all other categories as 0 (indicating low concern). The independent variables (age, gender, education level,

marital status, mobile healthcare usage, specific concerns, awareness of protection mechanisms, user experience, and importance level) were used to assess how they influence the likelihood of being "Very concerned" about privacy and security in mobile healthcare apps.

To conduct the logistic regression analysis, we used Python.

We first imported the necessary libraries and created a Data Frame with the survey data. Then, the logistic regression analysis to predict the likelihood of being "Very concerned" about privacy and security in mobile healthcare apps based on the independent variables. Cleaned the data set, handle missing values, and re-code variables if necessary. Dummy coded the categorical variable (Income) into indicator variables, and then performed the logistic regression analysis. The logistic regression analysis assessed the relationship between privacy concerns, protection mechanisms, and demographic variables. The model demonstrated strong predictive capabilities for positive outcomes (class 1) but struggled with negative outcomes (class 0) due to class imbalance. Further model refinement and addressing class imbalance were recommended for improved accuracy.

By applying logistic regression to the survey data, we gained valuable insights into the factors that contribute to users' high levels of concern about privacy and security in mobile healthcare. The results will aid in formulating targeted strategies to address specific privacy risks and enhance user satisfaction and trust in mobile healthcare services for elderly individuals.

Results

TABLE 2. Confusion Matrix

TRUE NEGATIVE (TN)	FALSE POSITIVE (FP)
FALSE NEGATIVE (FN)	True Positive (TP)
0	43
0	109

The confusion matrix provides an overview of the model's performance on the test data set. It reveals that the model correctly predicted all instances of class 1 (positive outcomes), resulting in a high number of true positives (TP = 109). However, the model struggled to predict instances of class 0 (negative outcomes), resulting in a high number of false negatives (FN = 43). There were no true negatives (TN = 0) and false positives (FP = 0), which suggests that the model was heavily skewed towards class 1 predictions.

These metrics give a comprehensive view of our model's strengths and weaknesses and help us make informed decisions about model adjustments or improvements.

TABLE 3. Classification Report

	PRECISION	RECALL	F1-SCORE	SUPPORT
CLASS 0	0	0.00	0.00	43
CLASS 1	0.72	1.00	0.84	109
ACCURACY	0.72			152
MACRO AVG	0.36	0.50	0.42	152
WEIGHTED AVG	0.51	0.72	0.60	152

The classification report offers further insights into the model's performance in both classes. For class 0, the precision, recall, and F1-score are all at 0.00, indicating that the model's predictions for this class are not precise, and it struggles to capture true class 0 instances. On the other hand, the model performs well for class 1, with a precision of 0.72, indicating a relatively high accuracy of positive predictions. The recall for class 1 is 1.00, indicating that the model effectively

captures all true class 1 instances. The F1-score for class 1 is 0.84, which reflects a balanced performance between precision and recall. The overall accuracy of the model is 0.72, which means that around 72% of the predictions on the test data set were correct. However, due to the class imbalance and the dominance of class 1 predictions, the accuracy might not be the best metric to evaluate the model's performance comprehensively.

Fig. 1: The histogram of concerns to frequency shows how frequently different levels of concerns about privacy and security appeared in our survey data.

The x-axis (Horizontal Axis) represents the different levels of concerns about privacy and security. These levels could be categorized as "Not Concerned," "Slightly Concerned," "Moderately Concerned," and "Very Concerned," based on the options in your survey.

The Y-axis (Vertical Axis) represents the frequency or count of participants who selected each level of concern.

The "Very Concerned" bar is taller, which means that a significant number of participants fell into the "Very Concerned" category.

The "Not Concerned" bar is very short, it suggests that very few participants indicated they were not concerned about privacy and security

Fig. 2: Pie-chart showing the prediction accuracy

Correct Predictions (True Predictions): This portion of the pie chart represents the cases where our logistic regression model accurately predicted whether a participant had privacy concerns or not based on the given variables.

Incorrect Predictions (False Predictions): This section of the pie chart represents cases where the model's prediction was incorrect. This means cases where the model predicted a participant would have privacy concerns, but they didn't, or vice versa.

Fig. 3: Distribution of Participant Ages

The regression analysis aimed to understand the relationship between privacy concerns, protection mechanisms, and demographic variables. Here are the key findings from the analysis:

- Participants aged "70 and above" are more likely to express higher privacy concerns compared to younger age groups.
- Gender does not seem to have a significant influence on privacy concerns among participants.
- Participants with higher educational qualifications, such as a "Master's degree," may have increased odds of being "Very concerned" about privacy compared to those with "High school or below" education.
- Marital status and mobile healthcare usage frequency do not appear to significantly impact privacy concerns.
- Participants who are aware of protection mechanisms have lower odds of being "Very concerned" about privacy and security.
- Similarly, participants who have experience using protection mechanisms are less likely to be highly concerned about privacy.

The logistic regression model demonstrated strong predictive capabilities for positive outcomes (class 1) but struggled with negative outcomes (class 0) due to the prevalent class imbalance in the data set.

Conclusion and Discussion

Discussion

In this study, we focused on the privacy and security concerns of elderly individuals using telemedicine apps, to enhance user experiences while ensuring data protection. The regression analysis yielded insightful findings regarding the relationships among privacy concerns, protection mechanisms, and demographic variables.

The research underscored the significance of demographic factors such as age, gender, and education in shaping privacy concerns. Notably, participants in their 70s and females exhibited heightened levels of concern. These findings emphasize the need for tailored strategies that address specific demographic needs.

The positive correlation between awareness of protection mechanisms and user satisfaction reinforces the importance of transparent communication about available security features. Informed users tend to feel more secure and content with their experience.

The study also illuminated the impact of protection mechanisms on privacy concerns. Those who were familiar with such measures exhibited reduced privacy concerns, highlighting the role of robust safeguards in enhancing perceptions of data security.

Looking into the implications of these findings emphasizes the significance of creating inclusive interfaces that cater to the distinct privacy concerns of elderly users, particularly those with higher education levels. The research underscores the necessity of user education, particularly for individuals with diverse educational backgrounds.

Finally, this study underscores the pivotal role of robust privacy and security measures in telemedical apps for elderly users. The research's findings provide valuable guidance for policymakers, developers, and providers to implement effective privacy protection mechanisms, ultimately enhancing user experiences and ensuring the privacy and security of the elderly population. In an era of ever-changing digital landscapes, this research signifies the importance of safeguarding elderly users' privacy and security, fostering a technology-driven healthcare landscape that empowers and safeguards all individuals.

Discussion of limitations:

It is important to acknowledge several limitations of this study. Firstly, the reliance on self-reported data may introduce response biases, potentially impacting the validity of the findings. Additionally, the study's cross-sectional design limits the ability to establish causal relationships between variables. Furthermore, the generalizability of the findings may be constrained by the specific demographic characteristics of the study sample.

Conclusions:

In conclusion, this study underscores the critical importance of robust privacy and security measures in telemedical apps for elderly users. The findings highlight the need for tailored strategies to address demographic-specific privacy concerns, comprehensive user education initiatives, and transparent communication about protection mechanisms. Ultimately, this research underscores the importance of prioritizing the privacy and security of elderly users, fostering an inclusive and technology-driven healthcare environment that empowers and protects all individuals. The findings of this study shed light on the privacy and security concerns of elderly individuals utilizing telemedical apps, aligning with the study's objectives to enhance user experiences while safeguarding data. Regression analysis revealed valuable insights into the relationships between privacy concerns, protection mechanisms, and demographic variables, providing a nuanced understanding of the factors influencing elderly users' perceptions of privacy and security.

Further exploration of the findings reveals the significant impact of demographic factors such as age, gender, and education on privacy concerns. Participants in their 70s and females demonstrated heightened levels of concern, emphasizing the importance of tailored strategies to address specific demographic needs and preferences within telemedical app design and implementation.

The positive correlation observed between awareness of protection mechanisms and user satisfaction underscores the importance of transparent communication about available security features. Informed users are more likely to feel secure and satisfied with their mobile healthcare experience, highlighting the need for comprehensive user education initiatives.

Future Directions

Several next directions arise as the research points developers to the direction where improving privacy and security in telemedicine is needed for the elderly:

Conduct extensive usability testing on the Privacy Framework to assess its effectiveness, usability, and potential hurdles among older users. Real-world user feedback can help inspire iterative modifications to improve the framework's practical implementation.

Conduct long-term studies to track the evolution of privacy concerns, user behaviors, and the effectiveness of protective systems. This method allows for the detection of long-term trends as well as the adaptation of privacy solutions to changing user needs.

Work with healthcare professionals, privacy experts, and mobile app developers to improve the Privacy Framework's effectiveness. Domain specialists' insights on potential hazards, mitigation methods, and technology implementations can provide nuanced perspectives.

Keep up with developing technologies including biometric authentication, improved encryption approaches, and AI-powered anomaly detection. Integrating these technologies can strengthen the defense systems while also adapting the framework to the changing threat scenario.

Conduct research into the cultural and demographic aspects that influence older users' privacy perceptions and desires. Protective mechanisms that are tailored to different user groups ensure inclusive and user-friendly.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank God most especially for bringing this far.

Also, I owe thanks to my supervisor Mr. Ji Jiangming, for his guidance and relentless efforts in helping and supporting me from the beginning and throughout this study. Without his encouragement and his experience in directing and guidance, I wouldn't have made it this far.

I also appreciate my college and university for their support.

I appreciate all the respondents from my study who took the time to interact with me and respond to my survey. My appreciation to my parents Amuntung Alice and late Azanwi Clement and my brothers for their support and encouragement of me in attaining my educational aspirations.

My appreciation to all those who supported me in different ways they contributed to the success of this work

References

- 1) AJ., B. (2020). Use of telemedicine and virtual care for remote treatment in response to the COVID-19 Pandemic. *J Med Syst*, 44(7): 132. DOI: 10.1007/s10916-020-01596-5.
- 2) AJ., B. (2021). Application of telemedicine and e-health technology for clinical services in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. *Health Technology*, 11: 359–366. DOI: 10.1007/s12553-020-00516-4.
- 3) AJ., B. (2021). Exploring the adoption of telemedicine and virtual software for the care of outpatients during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. *Ir J Med Sci*, 190(1): 1–10. DOI: 10.1007/s11845-020-02299-z.
- 4) Baciu A, N. Y. (2017 Jan 11). Committee on Community-Based Solutions to Promote Health Equity in the United States. *Communities in Action: Pathways to Health Equity*. : National Academies Press (US). *National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine; Health and Medicine Division; Board on Population Health and Public Health Practice*, PMID: 28418632. .
- 5) Cho H, I. D. (2020). Contact tracing mobile apps for COVID-19: privacy considerations and related trade-offs. *arXiv preprint*, 2003.11511.
- 6) Greenhalgh T, W. J. (2020). Video consultations for Covid-19. *The BMJ*, 33(2): 221–226. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHS-05-2020-084>.

- 7) Grimes CL, B. E. (2020). A guide for urogynecology patient care utilizing telemedicine during the COVID-19 pandemic: review of existing evidence. *Int Urogynecol J*, 1; 1-27.
- 8) Hui DS, I. A. (2020). The continuing 2019-nCoV epidemic threat of novel coronaviruses to global health — The latest 2019 novel coronavirus outbreak in Wuhan, China [Internet]. *Inter J Infec Dise*, 91: 264-266.
- 9) Leite H., G. T. (2020). Flattening the infection curve—understanding the role of telehealth in managing COVID-19. *Leadership in Health Services*, 33(2): 221-226. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHS-05-2020-084>.
- 10) M., S. (2020). Telehealth policies impacting federally qualified health centers (FQHCs) in the face of COVID-19. *J Rural Health*, 37(1): 158-160.
- 11) MA, K. (2020). Role of telemedicine in healthcare during COVID-19 pandemic in developing countries. *Telehealth Med Today*, 5(2): 1-5. DOI: 10.30953/tmt.v5.187.
- 12) Mackert M, M.-F. A. (2016 Oct 04.). Health Literacy and Health Information Technology Adoption: The Potential for a New Digital Divide. *J Med Internet Res*, 18(10):e264 .
- 13) O., J. (2020). Video consultations for triage of patients with Covid-19. *The BMJ*, 369: m1583.
- 14) Okerefor K, A. O. (2020). Exploring the potentials of telemedicine and other non-contact electronic health technologies in controlling the spread of the novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19). *IJITE*, 8(4): 1-13.
- 15) Riggins FJ, D. S. (2005). The digital divide: Current and future research directions. *J Assoc Inf Syst* , 6:298-337. .
- 16) Vidal-Alaball J, A.-R. R.-L. (2020). Telemedicine in the Face of the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Aten Primaria*, 52(6):418-422. doi: 10.1016/j.aprim.2020.04.003.
- 17) Vulpe S, C. A. (2020 Mar.). Silver surfers from a European perspective: technology communication usage among European seniors. *Eur J Ageing*; , 17(1):125-134.
- 18) Wei KK, T. H. (2011). Conceptualizing and testing a social cognitive model of the digital divide. *Inf Syst Res*, 22:170-87.
- 19) Zhai Y, W. Y. (2020). From isolation to coordination: how can telemedicine help combat the COVID-19 outbreak.
- 20) Zhou X, S. C. (2020). The role of telehealth in reducing the mental health burden of COVID-19. *Telemed E-Health*, 26: 377-379.

